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Statistical features on Riemannian Manifold

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Abstract:

Manifold are fundamental structures in different geometry. A smooth manifold with a metric is called a Riemannian Manifold. A connected Riemannian manifold carries the structure of metric space where distance function is the arc length of minimizing geodesic. In this paper, we consider finite dimensional manifold with a Riemannian metric as the basic structure. Based on this metric, we develop the notion of mean value, and covariance matrix of a random element, normal law mahalanobis distance and x^2 test.

Keywords: Riemannian Geometry, Riemannian metric, geodesic, statistics, probabilities Invariance.

1. Introduction:

Manifold is actually a topological space i.e. locally Euclidean according to ancient belief the earth was flat but modern evidence shows that it is round. This

variance arises from that fact that on the small scale that we see the earth does indeed look flat. In general any object that nearly flat on small scales is manifold so manifold constitute a generalization of object. We could live on in which we would encounter the round / flat.

1.1 Example of Manifold:

A Torus R^3 a sphere, an arbitrary curve or surface (in general an arbitrary n dimensional object), the surface human being.

1.2 Forms of Manifold:

- (i) A manifold can be compact (have boundaries) like a sphere or a cone.
- (ii) It can be infinite like R^3 , R^n , C^n .

1.3 Identification of Manifold:

In mathematical terminology locally each manifold resembles R^n .

At small distances it looks like the Euclidean R^2 but from far away it is S^2 , the two dimensional surface of a sphere.

1.4 The Three Instructions of Manifolds:

- a. Nearby points have nearby coordinates in at least one coordinate system.
- b. Every point has unique coordinates in each coordinate system that contains it.
- c. If two coordinate systems overlap, then in the region of the overlap, local coordinates of the point are related to each other in a sufficiently smooth way.

1.5 Tangent space on Manifolds:

Tangent Space is tangent to the Manifold. Each point on the manifold has its own Tangent Space. The Tangent Space has the same dimensionality as the manifold itself. The Tangent Space at the point P on manifold M is denoted by $T_{P_1}(M)$.

In our diagram, we show two tangent spaces on the manifold $T_{P_2}(M), T_{P_1}(M)$ at the points P_2 and P_1 respectively. A few example vectors are drawn in each Tangent Space. So we require at vectors othnly live in tangent spaces.

Tangent Space

1.6 Tangent space for m dimensional space:

The tangent space will be R^n . The displacement from one point to another. The displacement as the sum of small vectors (each in their own Tangent Space) adding up. Any vector in a tangent space can be expressed as a linear combination of the basis vectors for the tangent space.

Instead of one single vector in R^n , an arbitrary displacement now is the sum of any little vectors (each in their own tangent space)

In the mathematician's notation these basis vectors are written as

$$\left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2}, \dots, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^m} \right\}$$

The concept of partial derivatives captures the concept of basis vectors well. However we do not lose very much if we mentally convert the above expression to $\{\hat{e}_1(p), \hat{e}_2(p), \dots, \hat{e}_m(p)\}$ for understanding purposes.

1.7 Vector field on Manifolds:

A vector field in R^n means you have a vector at each point in space. The vector could be in an arbitrary direction. A vector field on a Manifold means that you have a vector at each point on the Manifold. However, the vector direction at a point can only be in any direction inside the Tangent space for that point.

1.8 Curvature and Parallel Transport:

A very intuitive understanding of curvature in space can be obtained by understanding parallel transport on S . Follow the vector along the path shown in the diagram. At each point, the vector is in the Tangent space of that point. We take care not to shift or twist the vector in any other way. We shift it “parallel to itself.”

Surprising thing happens. Over a closed path, the starting vector is different from the ending vector. When this happens, we say that the Manifold has curvature over the path. This phenomenon does not happen in R . We will now measure curvature mathematically. For that we need to understand covariant derivatives or a connection.

1.9 Covariant Derivative / Connection:

Suppose we have a smoothly varying vector (or a tensor) field over a Manifold. We should be able to capture the way it is changing by calculating its “derivative”. This derivative should have the same value regardless of the local coordinates we use to calculate it. In other words, we need to define a “covariant” derivative. The covariant derivative allows us express more complicated concepts like curvature and torsion in space.

Look at the Manifold in the above figure. It is a good example of a vector field. We centre our interest on how the vector field varies along the red dashed curve. The vector field at various points on the curve is shown by black arrows. How much is a vector field varying with respect to the vector at point P^n ? It is tough to say because the manifold has curvature (and we simply cannot subtract two vectors at different points on the Manifold to get a difference as we did in R). In order to compare the change we parallelly transport the vector from point P . The parallelly transported vector is depicted in green. Now we can calculate the difference Δv . In the case of covariant derivatives we are interested in change only in a particular direction and not over a curve. In our diagram the direction that we are interested in is w . We think of a covariant derivative of a vector field in the direction w .

Assume we are in some local coordinate system with coordinates x . We define the covariant derivative of a vector field $v(x)$ in direction w as:

$$\nabla_w v(x^\alpha) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{(v(x^\alpha + w^\alpha \varepsilon))_{\parallel} \text{transport to } x^\alpha - v(x^\alpha)}{\varepsilon}$$

Properties of the covariant derivative:

$$\nabla_{w+u} = \nabla_w + \nabla_u$$

$$\nabla_{\lambda w} = \lambda \nabla_w$$

$$\nabla_w (E + N) = \nabla_w E + \nabla_w N$$

Leibnitz Law:

$$\nabla_w (\lambda E) = \lambda \nabla_w E + E \nabla_w \lambda$$

Note: E, N are vector fields. λ is some scalar function.

1.10 Riemann Curvature:

Riemann curvature $R(L, M, N)$ where L, M, N are vector fields is defined as:

$$R(L, M, N) = \nabla_L \nabla_M N - \nabla_M \nabla_L N - \nabla_{[L, M]} N$$

$$[L, M] \equiv LM - ML$$

Note that R maps three vectors to a vector. In tensorial notation:

$$R(L, M, N) = L^a M^b N^c R_{abc}^d$$

R_{abc}^d is the Riemannian curvature tensor. Ricci Curvature R_{ac}

$$R_{ac} = R_{adc}^d$$

and Ricci Scalar S

$$S = g^{ac} R_{ac}$$

1.11 Riemannian Manifolds & Metrics:

Let M be a Manifold with a point p on it. Let T_p any two (M) be the Tangent Space at p . Let u, v be vectors in $T_p(M)$.

A metric at point p is a map that takes u, v as parameters and gives some number.

$$g_p(u, v) = \text{some number}$$

If $g_p(u, v) = g_p(v, u)$ and $g_p(u, u) \geq 0$ for all points in M then g is said to be a Riemannian Metric. A manifold with a Riemannian Metric is called a Riemannian Manifold.

Einstein took the solution of these equations to be of the form.

2. Probability density function:

Definition 1: Let A be the Borelian tribe of M . The random primitive x has a probability density function p_x (real, positive and integrable function) if $\forall X \in A$:

$$\Pr(x \in X) = \int_X p(y) \cdot dM(y) \text{ and } \Pr(M) = 1 \quad (1)$$

A simple example of a pdf is the *uniform pdf* in a bounded set X :

$$p_x(y) = 1_x(y) / V(X),$$

where $V(X)$ is the “volume” of the set X .

One must be careful that this pdf is uniform with respect to the measure dM and is not uniform for another measure on the manifold. This problem is the basis of the Bertrand paradox for geometrical probabilities [12, 6] and raise the problem of the measure to choose on the manifold. In our case, the measure is induced by the Riemannian metric but the problem is only lifted: which Riemannian metric do we have to choose? We addressed this question in [9] for transformation groups and homogeneous manifolds by showing that an invariant metric is a good geometric choice.

2.1 Expectation and Mean value:

Here, we focus on the notion of central value of a random primitive. We will preferably use the denomination *mean value or mean primitive* than *expected primitive* to stress the difference between this notion and the expectation of a real function.

2.2 Expectation of an observable:

Let $\varphi(x)$ be a Borelian real valued function defined on M and x a random primitive of pdf p_x . Then, $\varphi(x)$ is a real random variable and we can compute its expectation:

$$E[\varphi(x)] = E_x[\varphi] = \int_M \varphi(y) \cdot p_x(y) \cdot dM(y) \quad (2)$$

This notion of expectation corresponds to the one we defined on real random variables and vectors. However, we cannot directly extend it to define the mean value

of the distribution since we have no way to generalize this integral in R into an integral with value in the manifold.

2.3 Fréchet expectation or mean value:

Let x be a random vector of R^n . Fréchet observed in [3, 4] observed that the variance $\sigma_x^2(y) = E \text{ dist}(x, y)^2$ is minimized for the mean vector $\bar{x} = E[x]$. The major point for the generalization is that the expectation of a real valued function is well defined for our connected and geodesically complete Riemannian manifold M .

Definition 2 (Variance of a random primitive): Let x be a random primitive of pdf p_x . The variance $\sigma_x^2(y)$ is the expectation of the squared distance between the random primitive and the fixed primitive y :

$$\sigma_x^2(y) = E. \text{ dist}(y, x)^2 = \int_M \text{ dist}(y, z)^2 p_x(z). dM(z) \quad (3)$$

Definition 3 (Fréchet expectation of a random primitive): If the variance $\sigma_x^2(y)$ of a random primitive x is finite for all primitive $y \in M$, every primitive $\bar{x}$ minimizing this variance is called an expected of mean primitive. Thus, the set of the mean primitives is:

$$E[x] = \arg \min_{y \in M} E \text{ dist}(y, x)^2 \quad (4)$$

One can define other types of central values based on the *mean deviation at order α* : $\sqrt[\alpha]{E[\text{dist}(y, x)^\alpha]}$. For instance, the *modes* are obtained for $\alpha = 0$. Exactly like in a vector space, they are the primitives where the density is maximal on the manifold. The *median primitive* is obtained for $\alpha = 1$. For $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain the “barycenter” of the distribution support (which has to be compact).

3. Generalizing the Normal Law:

We now present an approach based on the information minimization to generalize the Normal distribution to a manifold. In this section the symbols $\log$ and $\exp$ denote the standard logarithmic and exponential functions in R .

3.1 Information and Uniform Law:

As we can integrate a real valued function, the extension of the *entropy* $H[x]$ (or its opposite, the *information* $I[x]$) of a random primitive is straightforward:

$$I[x] = -H[x] = E[\log(p_x(x))] \quad (5)$$

This definition is consistent since the pdf p_u that minimize the information when we only know that the measure is in a compact set u is the uniform density in this set.

3.2 Constrained information minimization:

Now assume that we know the mean (that we suppose to be unique) and the covariance of a random primitive: we denote it by $x \sim (\bar{x}, \Sigma)$. The least informative pdf minimizes the conditional information:

$$I[x | \bar{x} \in E[x], \Sigma_{xx} = \Sigma]$$

Expressing the normalization, fixed mean value and fixed covariance constraints in the exponential chart at the mean value and neglecting any continuity or differentiability constraint on the cut locus, we can write the Lagrangian in the vector space $T_x M$ and we obtain:

Theorem 1 (Normal Law): We call Normal law on the manifold M the pdf minimizing the information with a fixed mean value and covariance. Assuming no continuity nor differentiability constraint on the cut locus $C(\bar{x})$ and a symmetric domain $D(\bar{x})$, the Normal law of mean $\bar{x}$ and concentration matrix Γ is given by:

$$N_{(\bar{x}, \Gamma)}(y) = \left(k \cdot \exp - \frac{\vec{\bar{x}}y^T \cdot \Gamma \cdot \vec{\bar{x}}y}{2} \right) \quad (6)$$

where the normalization constant is

$$k^{(-1)} = \left(\int_M \exp - \frac{\vec{\bar{x}}y^T \cdot \Gamma \cdot \vec{\bar{x}}y}{2} \right) \cdot dM(y) \quad (7)$$

The covariance Σ and concentration Γ are related by:

$$\Sigma = \left(k \cdot \int_M \vec{\bar{x}}y \cdot \vec{\bar{x}}y^T \cdot \exp - \frac{\vec{\bar{x}}y^T \cdot \Gamma \cdot \vec{\bar{x}}y}{2} \right) \cdot dM(y) \quad (8)$$

From the concentration matrix, we can compute the covariance of the

random primitive, at least numerically, but the reverse is more difficult. Of course, in a vector space, the integrals can be entirely computed, and we find the usual Gaussian density.

3.3 Example on a simple manifold- the circle:

The exponential chart for the circle of radius 1 with the canonical metric is the angle with respect to the development point $\theta \in D =]-\pi; \pi[$, and the measure is simply $d\theta$. For a circle of radius r , the exponential chart becomes $x = r.\theta$. The domain is $D =]-a; a[$ (with $a = \pi.r$) and the measure is $dx = r.d\theta$. Thus, the normalization factor of the Normal density is:

$$k^{(-1)} = \int_{-a}^a \exp - \frac{\gamma.x^2}{2} . dx = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\gamma}} . \operatorname{erf} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{2}} . a$$

The density is the truncated Gaussian $N_{(0,\gamma)}(x)$ for $x \in]-a; a[$. It is continuous but not differentiable on the cut locus $\pi \equiv -\pi$. The truncation introduces a bias in the relation between the variance and the concentration parameter:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{\gamma} \left(1 - 2.a.k \cdot \exp - \frac{\gamma.a^2}{2} \right)$$

As the circle is compact, the variance cannot becomes infinite as in the real case when γ goes to zero: a Taylor expansion give $\sigma^2 = a^2/3 + O(\gamma)$. Thus, the maximal variance on the circle is $a^2/3$ with the density $N_{(0,0)}(x) = 1/(2a)$. As expected, the Normal density of concentration 0 is the uniform density. On the other hand, if γ goes to infinity, the variance goes to zero and the density tends to a Dirac (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Variance σ^2 with respect to the concentration parameter γ on the circle of radius 1 and the real line.

3.4 Approximated Normal Law:

If the pdf is sufficiently concentrated (a high concentration matrix Γ or a small covariance matrix Σ), then we can use the Taylor expansion of the metric in the exponential chart at the mean value given in [2, p. 84]. We easily deduce the Taylor expansion of the measure around the origin (Ric is the Ricci (or scalar) curvature matrix in the considered normal coordinate system):

$$dM(y) = \sqrt{\det(Q(y))} = 1 - \frac{y^T \cdot \text{Ric} \cdot y}{6} + O(\|y\|^3)$$

Reporting this Taylor expansion in the integrals and manipulating the formulas leads to the following theorem.

Theorem 2 (Approximate normal density): Let r be the injection radius at the mean point. The normalization constant and the concentration matrices are approximated by the following expressions for a small variance $\sigma^2 = \text{Tr}(\Sigma)$:

$$k = \frac{1 + O(\sigma^3) + \varepsilon \frac{\sigma}{r}}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^n \det(\Sigma)}} \quad ; \quad \Gamma = \Sigma^{(-1)} - \frac{\text{Ric}}{3} + O(\sigma) + \varepsilon \frac{\sigma}{r}$$

Here, $\varepsilon(x)$ is a function that is a $O(x^k)$ for any positive k , i.e. such that $\forall k \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $\lim_{0^+} x^{-k} \varepsilon(x) = 0$.

4. Mahalanobis Distance and χ^2 Law:

The problem we are now confronted with is to determine if a measure $\hat{y}$ was drawn from a random primitive $x \sim (\bar{x}, \Sigma_{xx})$. In the vectorial case and assuming a Gaussian distribution, the χ^2 test is well adapted to do that. This test measures the probability of the Mahalanobis distance $\chi^2 = (\hat{x} - \bar{x})^T \cdot \Sigma_{xx}^{(-1)} (\hat{x} - \bar{x})$ assuming that $\hat{x}$ is drawn from x . If the probability is too small (i.e. χ^2 is too large), the hypothesis is rejected.

Definition 4 (Mahalanobis distance): We call Mahalanobis distance between a random primitive $x \sim (\bar{x}, \Sigma_{xx})$ and a (deterministic) point y on the manifold the value

$$\mu_x^2(y) = \overrightarrow{\bar{x}y}^T \cdot \Sigma_{xx}^{(-1)} \overrightarrow{\bar{x}y} \tag{9}$$

In fact, the Mahalanobis distance measures the distance between y and the mean value $\bar{x}$ according to the “metric” $\Sigma_{xx}^{(-1)}$.

4.1 Properties:

Since μ_x^2 is a function from M to R , $\mu_x^2(y)$ is a real random variable. The expectation of this random variable is well defined and turns out to be quite simple:

$$E \mu_x^2(y) = \text{Tr} \Sigma_{xx}^{(-1)} \cdot \text{Cov}_{\bar{x}}(y)$$

The expectation of the Mahalanobis distance of a random primitive with itself is even simpler:

Theorem 3 (Mean Mahalanobis distance): The expected Mahalanobis distance of a random primitive with itself is independent of the distribution and does only depend on the dimension of the manifold: $E \mu_x^2(x) = n$.

This identity can be used to verify with a posteriori measurements that the covariance matrix has been correctly estimated. It can be compared with the expectation of the “normalized” squared distance, which is by definition: $E \text{dist}(x, \bar{x})^2 / \sigma_x^2(x) = 1$.

4.2 A generalized χ^2 law:

Assuming that the random primitive $x \sim (\bar{x}, \Sigma_{xx})$ is normal, we can go one step further and compute the probability that $\chi^2 = \mu_x^2 < \alpha^2$. This generalization of the χ^2 law turns out to be still independent of the mean value and the covariance matrix of the random primitive (at least up to the order $O(\sigma^3)$):

Theorem 4 (Approximate χ^2 law): With the same hypotheses as for the approximate normal law, the χ^2 density probability function is

$$p\chi^2(u) = \frac{1 + O(\sigma^3) + \varepsilon \frac{\sigma}{r}}{2 \cdot \Gamma^{n/2}} \frac{u^{\frac{n}{2}-1}}{2} \exp - \frac{u}{2} \tag{10}$$

Thus, up to the third order, the χ^2 law on a Riemannian manifold can be approximated by the standard χ^2 law.

References:

- [1] M. do Carmo : *Riemannian Geometry*, Mathematics, Birkhäuser, Boston, Basel, Berlin, 1992.
- [2] I. Chavel : *Riemannian geometry - A modern introduction*, Volume 108 of Cambridge tracts in mathematics, Cambridge University Press, 1993.
- [3] M. Fréchet : *L'intégrale abstraite d'une fonction abstraite d'une variable abstraite et son application a la moyenne d'un élément aléatoire de nature quelconque*, Revue Scientifique, pages 483-512, 1944.
- [4] M. Fréchet : *Les éléments aléatoires de nature quelconque dans un espace distancié*, Ann. Inst. H. Poincaré, 10: 215-310, 1948.
- [5] H. Karcher : *Riemannian center of mass and mollifier smoothing*, Comm. Pure Appl. Math, 30: 509-541, 1977.
- [6] M.G. Kendall and P.A.P. Moran : *Geometrical Probability Number 10 in Griffin's statistical monographs and courses*, Charles Griffin & Co. Ltd., 1963.
- [7] W.S. Kendall : *Probability, convexity, and harmonic maps with small image i : uniqueness and fine existence*. Proc. London Math. Soc., 61(2): 371-406, 1990.
- [8] W. Klingenberg : *Riemannian Geometry*. Walter de Gruyter, Berlin, New York, 1982.
- [9] X. Pennec and N. Ayache : *Uniform distribution, distance and expectation problems for geometric features processing*. Journal of Mathematical Imaging and Vision, 9(1): 49-67, July 1998.
- [10] X. Pennec and J.-P. Thirion : *A framework for uncertainty and validation of 3D registration methods based on points and frames*. Int. Journal of Computer Vision. 25(3): 203-229, 1997.
- [11] Xavier Pennec : *L'Incertitude dans les Problèmes de Reconnaissance et de Recalage - Applications en Imagerie Médicale et Biologie Moléculaire*. PhD thesis, Ecole Polytechnique, Palaiseau (France), December 1996.
- [12] H. Poincaré : *Calcul des probabilités*, 2nd edition, Paris, 1912.